

Conference Abstract

A Use Case Approach to Integrate Ecological Research Networks and Infrastructures to Advance Macro-system Science

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Abstract

We explore how the Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (GERI) proposes a pathway for other Networks and Networks-of-Networks (NoNs) can work together and accelerate collaborations and data harmonization to address global environmental challenges. Recognizing that contemporary environmental issues transcend geopolitical boundaries, we advocate for collaborative frameworks that integrate top-down structured ecosystems research infrastructures (ERIs) with bottom-up environmental networks (ENs). We highlight the unique characteristics of ERIs, including their long-term data collection capabilities and structured governance, in contrast to the flexible and innovative nature of ENs. We address the technical and organizational barriers that hinder effective collaboration and data sharing among these entities and draw upon two use cases:

1. ecological drought; and
2. the integration of Mexican ENs into a NoNs framework.

Through workshops and strategic leadership tools, we established a shared understanding and collective identity among these diverse stakeholders, and fostered sustainable organizational practices and enhanced global environmental observations. Our findings underscore the importance of addressing cultural dynamics and building mutual trust to ensure the long-term sustainability of collaborative efforts in ecological research and data integration. Together top-down ERIs that support standardized and long-term observational continuity, and bottom-up ENs that introduce new perspectives and data types, provide the complementarity to support the data and human capital required to address the *Grand Challenges* of global environmental change.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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